

Quantifying and explaining uncertainty in official small-area population estimates

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Summary

Official small-area population estimates underpin urban analytics and policy, yet their reliability varies across space and time. We introduce a computational framework to quantify three uncertainty components: (i) revision-based instability across release vintages, (ii) volatility-based instability across consecutive years, and (iii) scale-based sensitivity to spatial support. For England and Wales, we model these uncertainties against census data, deprivation indices, and geodemographic covariates. Results show that volatility aligns with observed local context, whereas revisions are weak under global covariates but become better explained once spatial dependence is modelled. Furthermore, aggregation from finer to coarser spatial scales consistently attenuates uncertainty across diagnostics.

KEYWORDS: Small-area population estimates; uncertainty; revision instability; temporal volatility; scale sensitivity.

1 Introduction

Small-area population estimates (SAPE) support a broad range of geographical and urban analytics, including service accessibility, neighbourhood change, health inequalities, disaster risk assessment, and the allocation of public resources (Longley, 2012; Lloyd, 2016; Wilson et al., 2022). In England and Wales, SAPEs are published annually for multiple statistical geographies and are commonly treated as stable inputs to downstream modelling and decision-making, yet their reliability is not spatially uniform and can vary over time (Office for National Statistics, 2023). Areas characterised by high residential churn, sizeable student or communal-establishment populations, complex household structures, and rapidly changing urban functions are persistently difficult to measure, often coinciding with places where administrative and survey data are incomplete, delayed, or revised (Lansley et al., 2019; Hand, 2018).

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This implies a key methodological challenge: SAPE uncertainty is multi-dimensional. First, estimates for a fixed reference year can change across release vintages as new data sources are incorporated, constraints are updated, and methods are refined (Office for National Statistics, 2023). Second, estimates may exhibit substantial temporal instability across consecutive years, reflecting both demographic change and the estimation system’s sensitivity to local signals. Third, the magnitude and geography of uncertainty can depend on spatial scales, reflecting the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) and ecological effects (Lan et al., 2020; Kwan, 2012). Despite their practical importance, these dimensions are rarely operationalised and compared within a unified framework.

This study introduces a computational framework that formalises three complementary notions of uncertainty in SAPE:

- Revision-based uncertainty: instability of estimates for the same reference year across different release vintages (e.g., initial versus revised releases), operationalised through cross-vintage discrepancies for matched geographies.
- Volatility-based uncertainty: temporal instability across consecutive reference years within a vintage, capturing year-on-year fluctuation and local instability patterns.
- Scale-based uncertainty: sensitivity of uncertainty patterns to spatial aggregation, such as LSOA vs. MSOA.

To examine the extent to which these uncertainties are attributable to observed local structure, we link uncertainty diagnostics to an interpretable set of covariates compiled at the LSOA21 level. The main covariates are engineered from Census 2021 topic summary tables to capture mechanisms plausibly associated with estimation difficulty and demographic churn. We then augment these with contextual measures, i.e., deprivation indices (IMD¹ 2025, Index of Multiple Deprivation) and geodemographic neighbourhood typologies (OAC 2021, Output Area Classification) (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2025; Wyszomierski et al., 2024). A staged modelling design is used to evaluate the incremental explanatory contribution of each covariate family, separating the information content of census structure from that of deprivation and neighbourhood classification.

2 Methods

2.1 Uncertainty metrics

We compile official SAPE for England and Wales on 2021 Census geographies at scales $g \in \{\text{LSOA}, \text{MSOA}\}$. For revision-based uncertainty, we focus on $t^* = \text{mid-2022}$ and assemble three SAPE vintages $v_1 < v_2 < v_3$ (19 Mar 2024; 25 Nov 2024; 7 Nov 2025), enabling cross-vintage comparison on matched geographies. The volatility window spans from mid-2020 to mid-2024. Let $P_{i,t}^{(v,g)}$ denote the published estimate for unit i (scale g) and year t from vintage v . These diagnos-

¹Deprivation is captured by nation-specific indices (the Index of Multiple Deprivation for England and the Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation for Wales). For simplicity, we refer to both collectively as IMD throughout.

tics are designed to separate instability arising from retrospective revision, inter-annual fluctuation, and spatial aggregation, while remaining directly computable from routinely published official estimates.

2.1.1 Revision-based uncertainty.

For t^* , we define the signed revision between two vintages $v_a \prec v_b$ as

$$r_i^{(a,b,g)} = P_{i,t^*}^{(v_b,g)} - P_{i,t^*}^{(v_a,g)}. \quad (1)$$

Then, we summarise revision intensity by the late–early relative revision

$$R_i^{(g)} = \frac{|P_{i,t^*}^{(v_3,g)} - P_{i,t^*}^{(v_1,g)}|}{P_{i,t^*}^{(v_3,g)}}, \quad (2)$$

and the robust cross-vintage dispersion

$$S_i^{(g)} = \frac{\text{MAD}\left(P_{i,t^*}^{(v_1,g)}, P_{i,t^*}^{(v_2,g)}, P_{i,t^*}^{(v_3,g)}\right)}{P_{i,t^*}^{(v_3,g)}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\text{MAD}(\cdot)$ denotes the median absolute deviation.

2.1.2 Volatility-based uncertainty

Let $\mathcal{T} = \{2020, \dots, 2024\}$. To avoid conflating volatility with revision effects, each year-on-year ratio is computed using $P_{i,t}$ and $P_{i,t-1}$ taken from the same SAPE release for that t . Define the log growth rate

$$g_{i,t}^{(g)} = \log\left(\frac{P_{i,t}^{(g)}}{P_{i,t-1}^{(g)}}\right), \quad t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{2020\}, \quad (4)$$

and the robust volatility metric

$$V_i^{(g)} = \text{MAD}_t\left(g_{i,t}^{(g)}\right). \quad (5)$$

As a mechanism-aligned complement that controls for LAD totals, we define within-LAD shares

$$s_{i,t}^{(g)} = \frac{P_{i,t}^{(g)}}{P_{\text{LAD}(i),t}^{\text{LAD}}}, \quad (6)$$

and quantify within-LAD redistribution volatility by

$$V_{i,\text{share}}^{(g)} = \text{MAD}_t\left(\Delta \log s_{i,t}^{(g)}\right), \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta \log s_{i,t}^{(g)} = \log s_{i,t}^{(g)} - \log s_{i,t-1}^{(g)}$.

2.1.3 Scale-based uncertainty

Scale-based uncertainty evaluates how uncertainty diagnostics depend on spatial support. We compute $\{R_i^{(g)}, S_i^{(g)}, V_i^{(g)}, V_{i,\text{share}}^{(g)}\}$ separately for each $g \in \{\text{LSOA}, \text{MSOA}\}$ and compare their distributions and spatial patterns across scales. To summarise how aggregation attenuates (or amplifies) uncertainty, we use quantile attenuation profiles:

$$A_{g_2 \leftarrow g_1}^U(\tau) = \frac{Q_\tau(U^{(g_2)})}{Q_\tau(U^{(g_1)})}, \quad \tau \in \mathcal{Q}, \quad g_1 \rightarrow g_2 \in \{\text{LSOA} \rightarrow \text{MSOA}\}, \quad (8)$$

where $U \in \{R, S, V, V_{\text{share}}\}$ and $Q_\tau(\cdot)$ denotes the empirical τ -quantile across all units at a given scale. Values below one indicate attenuation under aggregation, while values above one indicate amplification at coarser scales.

2.2 Covariates and models

We assemble an interpretable covariate set to support attribution of uncertainty patterns in small-area population estimates. For comparability of effect sizes and numerical stability, continuous covariates are standardised using a global z-score, while categorical indicators are entered as unstandardised dummies. Our covariates fall into three families. First, we engineer a set of demographic and housing-structure measures from Census 2021 topic summary tables, designed to capture mechanisms plausibly related to estimation difficulty (Table 1). In particular, we include housing proxies related to tenure and dwelling type (e.g., private renting and flat-like accommodation shares), which are salient dimensions in the design of UK census output geographies (Martin et al., 2001). Second, we incorporate neighbourhood deprivation using IMD 2025 at LSOA21. Third, we add geodemographic context via OAC neighbourhood typologies (encoded as a set of binary indicator variables at a chosen hierarchy level).

Table 1: Census 2021 covariates engineered at LSOA21 (England and Wales).

Covariates	Source	Definition
x_i^{comm}	TS001	$\log(1 + 1000 \cdot (\text{Communal}/\text{Total}))$
x_i^{stu}	TS068	Student share among residents aged 5+
x_i^{mig}	TS019	$1 - \text{SameAddr}/\text{Total}$ (any move in last year)
x_i^{abroad}	TS019	Abroad/Total (moved from outside UK)
x_i^{pr}	TS054	Private rented households share
x_i^{flat}	TS044	Flat-like accommodation share
x_i^{1p}	TS017	One-person share among occupied household spaces
x_i^{15-24}	TS007A	Age 15–24 share
x_i^{65+}	TS007A	Age 65+ share

We relate each uncertainty metric to the covariate set using both global and local regression models. First, we fit a global ordinary least squares (OLS) specification as a transparent baseline, report-

ing heteroskedasticity-robust (HC3) inference. Second, to assess spatially varying associations and spatial dependence, we fit a geographically weighted spatial autoregressive model (GW-SAR), estimated using British National Grid centroid coordinates with an adaptive kernel and data-driven bandwidth selection (Wang et al., 2020).

3 Results

3.1 Explaining uncertainty at the LSOA scale

Figure 1 provides context for the study region and the uncertainty constructs at the LSOA scale, illustrating that both revisions and year-to-year changes are spatially structured.

Figure 1: Overview of study region and population estimates at LSOA21. (a) shows Mid-2022 SAPE (latest vintage, v3). (b1) and (b2) map cross-vintage differences for Mid-2022 (v3-v2 and v2-v1). (c1) and (c2) show SAPE levels for Mid-2020 and Mid-2024, respectively, providing context for temporal variation.

Table 2 summarises explained variance across the staged feature sets. In the global OLS specification, the revision-based diagnostics are only weakly explained: R^2 stays below 0.04 for both R_i and S_i across stages, suggesting that cross-sectional covariates alone capture little of the cross-vintage discrepancies for a fixed reference year. By contrast, the volatility-based diagnostics are consistently more explainable under OLS (around $R^2 \approx 0.22$ for V_i and $R^2 \approx 0.21$ for V_i^{share}), indicating that

inter-annual instability is more strongly aligned with observable local context. Adding IMD and OAC leads to only modest changes in this global baseline, implying that much of the explainable signal is already present in the core covariate set under a fixed-coefficient model.

Allowing for spatial dependence via GW-SAR yields a substantial improvement for all outcomes. In the Stage 4 specification (Census + IMD + OAC), GW-SAR achieves $R^2 = 0.433$ for R_i and 0.397 for S_i , and $R^2 = 0.572$ and 0.559 for V_i and V_i^{share} , respectively. The gain relative to OLS is particularly pronounced for the revision-based diagnostics, consistent with revisions being dominated by spatially structured processes that are not well captured by purely global covariates. Overall, the staged comparison indicates that volatility is meaningfully attributable to measured local conditions even in global models, whereas explaining revision patterns requires accounting for spatial dependence and contextual covariates, pointing to an important role for spatially structured estimation mechanisms.

Table 2: Explained variance (R^2) across staged feature sets (LSOA21; $n = 35,672$). Stage 1: Census; Stage 2: Census + IMD; Stage 3: Census + OAC; Stage 4: Census + IMD + OAC.

	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
<i>(a) OLS</i>				
R_i	0.015	0.015	0.016	0.016
S_i	0.031	0.031	0.033	0.033
V_i	0.223	0.226	0.225	0.228
V_i^{share}	0.210	0.211	0.211	0.213
<i>(b) GW-SAR</i>				
R_i	0.325	0.347	0.413	0.433
S_i	0.279	0.305	0.373	0.397
V_i	0.490	0.509	0.553	0.572
V_i^{share}	0.475	0.494	0.542	0.559

3.2 Scale-based uncertainty: LSOA to MSOA

Scale-based uncertainty evaluates how uncertainty diagnostics depend on spatial support. For the LSOA21→MSOA21 comparison, we summarise aggregation effects using the quantile attenuation profile $A_{\text{MSOA} \leftarrow \text{LSOA}}^U(\tau)$ (Eq. 8). In interpreting scale effects in the UK context, it is also relevant that census output geographies were deliberately designed using zone-design principles (after Openshaw) to satisfy population constraints while improving compactness and internal homogeneity (Martin et al., 2001).

Across all four diagnostics, aggregation produces substantial and broadly uniform attenuation: median attenuation ratios $A(0.50)$ are around 0.51-0.56, and IQR ratios are around 0.53-0.60 (Table 3). Attenuation is similar at the lower and upper quartiles, with $A(0.25)$ and $A(0.75)$ closely aligned with the median attenuation across all diagnostics, indicating no disproportionate compression of

either tail. Overall, moving to a coarser scale reduces both the typical magnitude of uncertainty and its cross-area dispersion.

Table 3: Scale-based uncertainty from LSOA21 to MSOA21. It reports medians at each scale and distributional attenuation under aggregation using quantile ratios $A(\tau)$ and the IQR ratio.

Metric	Median (LSOA)	Median (MSOA)	$A(0.25)$	$A(0.50)$	$A(0.75)$	IQR ratio
R_i	0.54%	0.28%	0.519	0.524	0.527	0.530
S_i	0.13%	0.07%	0.474	0.522	0.545	0.569
V_i	0.84	0.47	0.556	0.556	0.580	0.596
V_i^{share}	0.83	0.43	0.513	0.518	0.533	0.545

Notes: Medians are computed across all areas at each scale: R_i, S_i in % (values $\times 100$); V_i, V_i^{share} in log-points $\times 100$.

4 Conclusion

We present a computational framework for diagnosing uncertainty in official small-area population estimates as a spatially structured phenomenon. In England and Wales, global covariates explain a meaningful share of volatility but little of revision-based discrepancies, whereas allowing for spatial dependence markedly improves fit for both, indicating that revisions are driven in part by spatially structured estimation mechanisms and reallocation processes. In addition, we found that aggregation from LSOA to MSOA attenuates uncertainty by about half across diagnostics. These findings motivate uncertainty-aware use of SAPE in downstream urban analytics and provide a transferable basis for extending diagnostics to additional scales and future releases.

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Biography

Yatao Zhang is a Senior Research Fellow at the Department of Geography, University College London. He received his doctoral degree in Geomatics Engineering from ETH Zurich in 2025. His research sits at the intersection of GeoAI and urban analytics, with a specific focus on spatiotemporal context modeling across urban transportation, land use, and geodemographics.

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